

ОСНОВНЫЕ ПРИНЦИПЫ И НОВЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ ЗЕЛеноЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ

Сорокина А., Суходольская Д.

Белорусский национальный технический университет, Заведующий кафедрой, Канд.
Педагог. Наук, доцент

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11032862>

Аннотация. Основной темой данной статьи является насущность вопроса изучения и развития устойчивой экономики, возможные меры для ее достижения, а также рассмотрение инновационных решений для сокращения вредоносного воздействия на окружающую среду.

Ключевые слова: зеленая экономика, меры по достижению устойчивой экономики, альтернативные источники энергии, охрана окружающей среды, возобновляемые источники энергии, зеленая авиация, искусственный интеллект.

BASIC PRINCIPLES AND NEW TECHNOLOGIES OF GREEN ECONOMY

Sorokina A., Sukhodolskaya D.

Annotation. the main topic of this article is the urgency of studying and developing a sustainable economy, possible measures to achieve it, as well as consideration of innovative solutions to reduce harmful effects on the environment.

Keywords: green economy, measures to achieve a sustainable economy, alternative energy sources, environmental protection, renewable energy sources, green aviation, artificial intelligence.

In the 21st century, the importance of green economy is becoming increasingly relevant due to the threat of climate change, high levels of environmental pollution, and depletion of natural resources. Green economy represents a model of economic development that aims at sustainable use of natural resources (particularly oil, gas, and coal), reduction of harmful emissions and job creation in the renewable energy sector. Therefore, it can be concluded that the main goal of green economy is to promote the development of a sustainable and efficient model of production and consumption.

As a rule, the main principles of green economy include improving energy efficiency in production, developing renewable energy sources, increasing the share of environmentally friendly technologies and stimulating innovations in the field of environmentally sustainable production and consumption. The application of these principles makes it possible to solve key problems related to the possibility of developing a sustainable economy: reducing greenhouse gas emissions and anthropogenic impact on the environment, therefore, improving air and water quality, reducing soil pollution and the amount of accumulated industrial waste and, ultimately, improving the standard of living of the population. Based on this, the following possible measures can be identified to achieve and develop a sustainable economy:

1. The transition from the use of non-ecological sources of energy such as oil and coal to more environmentally friendly alternatives. In the light of the current environmental situation in the world (threats of climate change and exhaustion of traditional energy resources) it became obvious that humanity needs to switch to renewable (alternative) energy sources (RES) – energy from the sun, wind, water, tides, gradient temperature, geothermal, hydrogen and bioenergy [1].

The use of such sources is considered progressive and contributes to reducing the use of limited natural resources, however, most of the above-mentioned types of sources are still in the development stage, and are limited by regional suitability, therefore, solar, wind energy and energy obtained from hydroelectric power stations, which are considered the main ones.

2. Reducing the volume of increasing traffic and using public transport to combine trips for shopping.

3. Environmental protection. This measure involves the need for the development of legislation and standards at the state and international levels and requires coordination of actions by government agencies, business and the public. Government agencies can create incentives for the development of green economy, such as tax incentives, subsidies for the development and promotion of renewable energy sources, various innovations that make more efficient use of water and other natural resources, as well as the introduction of standards at the level of the European Union.

Of course, the use of alternative energy sources is a progressive phenomenon that contributes to reducing the consumption of limited natural resources. However, it should be understood that new technologies, due to their evolving nature, can have their own negative consequences. For example, the disadvantages of solar energy include the use of poisonous and toxic substances that often accompany the creation of solar panels and which can be released into the environment, it creates a problem of their disposal [2]. The use of wind turbines can cause radio interference, which leads to jamming of station signals, and disrupt the ecosystem of the area in which they are located: ornithologists noted that wind turbines create obstacles to the migration of birds and insects. Also, the urgent problem of using alternative energy is its high cost – the purchase of special equipment, the allocation and preparation of large areas for the construction of power plants, direct dependence on weather conditions (intensity of solar radiation, ambient temperature, variability of wind power, etc.).

Realizing the necessity of avoiding and reducing the negative consequences of anthropogenic impact on the environment, developments are underway around the world to create the latest technologies to solve environmental problems:

1. Innovations in land transport, plastic roads

According to statistics, Tesla Models are the best-selling electric vehicles in the world: in 2018, the number of manufactured electric vehicles amounted to 245 thousand, which indicates the increasing popularity of this transport among consumers [3]. The essence of the work of electric vehicles lies in their functioning due to batteries charged with electricity, which solves the problem of greenhouse gas emissions. However, electric cars are not entirely harmless to the environment: often the energy powering the car is generated at non-ecological power stations that run on limited fossil fuels. In addition, scientists are faced with the task of solving the issue of safely disposing of the batteries from electric vehicles, only after solving which it will be possible to judge the complete ecological purity of this type of transport. At the moment, developments are also underway to improve the current charging infrastructure and the electric vehicle power system – they are unable to hold a charge for long enough, therefore, to ensure a complete transition to an electric future.

Along with electric vehicles, cars, buses and trains powered by hydrogen fuel are also produced around the world today, which, according to scientists, will also significantly reduce the consumption of fossil hydrocarbons. The Italian company GF Biochemicals was the first to produce levulinic acid on an industrial scale and is now developing biofuels based on it which is capable of replacing gasoline [4].

The idea of replacing asphalt with plastic is relatively new and is being actively implemented in large cities during road construction, thanks to its simplicity and cost-

effectiveness. For example, plastic pavement projects are underway in Pakistan, which is interested in introducing a circular waste economy.

Modules made of recycled plastic are lightweight and easily connected to each other, after which they are equipped with all necessary communications. One of the manufacturers of such modules is the Dutch company Plastic Road – it was one of the first to develop modules and assemble roads from them [5].

2. Green aviation

In the modern world, the problem of environmental sustainability is becoming particularly relevant, including in the context of air transport. One of the aspirations of the aviation industry is the development and implementation of environmentally friendly aircraft. This line of research is aimed at creating aircraft that would be more efficient in using resources. One of the key methods of reducing the harmful effects of aviation on the environment is the improvement of aircraft engines. Work in this area includes the development of technologies to reduce emissions of harmful substances and reduce fuel consumption. The first environmentally friendly manned aircraft was created in 2009 [6]. The Solar Impulse aircraft operated using solar energy collected with the help of solar cells on the wings and stored in batteries; and it stayed in the air for more than ten hours.

3. Artificial intelligence

AI is a powerful tool for optimizing processes and increasing efficiency in implementing the principles of sustainable development. The use of AI in the management of energy systems enables more accurate prediction of energy consumption, optimization of electricity production and distribution, which helps to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and increase the efficiency of renewable energy sources. Thus, various enterprises equip their production facilities with sensors that track the production process and environmental monitoring systems to monitor temperature, air humidity, soil, noise levels, radioactive contamination, etc.

Another example is agriculture, where the use of artificial intelligence makes it possible to optimize tillage processes, control irrigation levels, improve crop quality and reduce the use of chemical fertilizers. This helps to increase yields with more environmentally friendly farming methods. For example, in Europe, the smart soil irrigation system WaterBee is used, which is able to assess the condition of the soil and analyze the need and time of irrigation.

Artificial intelligence is also used to systematize the waste collection and recycling process. With the help of the Internet of Things, the fullness of garbage containers and their timely cleaning are monitored everywhere by calling an operator. Examples of successful integration of this program are the American Bigbelly system, the Russian Perekrestok system and MTS.

The smart home system (city, factory) is of interest to both businesses and ordinary consumers, as it is aimed at caring for nature through economical electricity consumption. Based on research conducted by the French company Schneider Electric, the industrial Internet of Things allows you to reduce energy consumption by up to 24% [7].

Thus, research shows that the transition to a green economy can bring significant economic benefits, including reducing energy and resource costs, increasing the competitiveness of enterprises and increasing investments in environmentally sustainable projects. Another advantage of green economy is its ability to improve the quality of life and health of the population and to promote the development of new technologies and innovations, which contributes to economic growth and promotes job creation. Green economy is an important tool for achieving sustainable development and preserving the natural environment for future generations.

References

1. Что такое альтернативные источники энергии и какое у них будущее [Electronic resource]. — Mode of access: <https://trends.rbc.ru/trends/green/609e76449a7947f4755ac9dc>. — Date of access: 18.03.2024.
2. Альтернативные источники энергии: виды и использование [Electronic resource]. — Mode of access: <https://www.irb.basnet.by/ru/alternativnyie-istochniki-energii-vidy-i-ispolzovanie/> — Date of access: 20.03.2024.
3. 20 инноваций, которые спасут нашу планету [Electronic resource]. — Mode of access: <https://naked-science.ru/article/hi-tech/20-innovatsi?ysclid=lu5pn3ugd927513797>. — Date of access: 21.03.2024.
4. Какие альтернативные источники уже существуют [Electronic resource]. — Mode of access: <https://meduza.io/feature/2015/12/27/biomaslo-kislota-i-sila-kosmosa?ysclid=lu9vgbkqy889692484>. — Date of access: 21.03.2024.
5. Зеленые технологии, которые позволяют сохранить природу [Electronic resource]. — Mode of access: <https://invlab.ru/tehnologii/zelyonye-tehnologii/?ysclid=lu5pncvwjv429228630>. — Date of access: 21.03.2024.
6. 20 инноваций, которые спасут нашу планету [Electronic resource]. — Mode of access: <https://naked-science.ru/article/hi-tech/20-innovatsi?ysclid=lu5pn3ugd927513797>. — Date of access: 21.03.2024.
7. Экологический фронт [Electronic resource]. — Mode of access: <https://inlnk.ru/KezAD1>. — Date of access: 22.03.2024.